

Validation of Task Items on a Screener for Initial Algebra

Aoife OBrien¹ and Máire Ní Ríordáin²

¹Galway-Mayo Institute of Technology and ²University College Cork

A standardised criterion referenced assessment known as a screener has been developed for initial algebra. This screener is a formative assessment which has been designed to be of use to teachers in the second-year Irish post-primary mathematics classroom. This paper outlines the design of the screener as guided by the assessment triangle and the subsequent steps in selecting and validating task items for use on the screener. There are two types of items included - selected response (SR) and constructed response (CR). Classical Test Theory (CTT) is used to analyze the results of the SR task items in terms of item difficulty, discrimination, and functioning distractors. Important construct validity evidence arises from the statistical analyses of the item responses. The results of these analyses inform the presentation and layout of the SR task items on the final draft of the screener to ensure the construct of initial algebra is operationalised fairly.

Introduction

Initial algebra is the period when students transition from arithmetic to algebra, an area of mathematics education known for its difficulties (Kieran, 2007). Much research and effort has been focused on the area of algebraic thinking and initial algebra to improve students' engagement and attainment with the subject (Kieran et al., 2016). Formative assessment (FA) should now be a vital part of mathematics teaching and learning and it should form part of the "Assessment toolkit" for all classrooms (NCCA, 2019). However, it is noted in the literature that few adequate assessments are available to provide formative information on a student's progress with algebra, but they are essential to allow timely and informed instructional decisions for teachers (Ketterlin-Geller et al., 2019). The overall aim of this study was to profile second year post-primary students' (approx. age 14) knowledge of initial algebra and to do so an appropriate measurement instrument was required. This standardised screener developed for this study takes the form of a summative assessment (SA) to be used in a formative manner, as it can provide information to teachers about their students' current understanding of algebra and identify any gaps in their knowledge and understanding. The focus of this paper is on the development and validation of selected response (SR) task items for the standardised screener. First the design of the screener is outlined which explains how the task items were identified and selected for inclusion. Subsequently, the methodology employed to establish construct validity using item level analysis is given. Finally, an overview of the results of item analyses are presented and the resulting changes to the screener are documented.

Screener Design and Development

Nichols et al., (2017) state that assessment design is a "sequence of development actions aimed at accomplishing specific goals" and assessment development is "the execution of the planned course of action" (p. 15). The assessment triangle as described by Pellegrino et

al. (2001) guided the many interconnected decisions in the design and development of the screener. The assessment triangle consists of three interconnected elements; (i) Cognition; a theory of how students gain competence in a domain, (ii) Observation; the task items or content used to evidence the learning and cognition, (iii) Interpretation; the methods used to interpret and analyse the evidence (Nichols et al., 2017).

The cognition vertex of the assessment triangle is addressed by establishing the construct of interest. This is done by aligning the knowledge, skills, and abilities (KSAs) required for initial algebra with an appropriate conceptual framework. An established framework for algebraic thinking by Kaput et al., (2008) was identified in the literature which aligns closely with the Junior Cycle specification. Research by Blanton et al. (2018) to develop a framework for algebra organises Kaput's two core aspects into the following three areas (i) generalised arithmetic, (ii) equivalence, expressions, equations, and inequalities, and (iii) functional thinking. This was adopted as the conceptual model for initial algebra in this study. Related content domains from the Irish syllabus were used as a framework to align the prerequisite and algebra content areas identified in the literature (O' Brien & Ní Ríordáin, 2017). These content areas framed the pertinent KSAs required for success in algebra as guided by the conceptual framework adopted for this study.

Cronbach and Meehl (1955) state that the construct to be measured consists of a universe of content, from which items that are domain relevant should be sampled, and from these a test that is representative of the domain can be developed. By defining the construct of interest "initial algebra" and using a conceptual model aligned with relevant content areas and the Irish syllabus a systematic search of the literature for studies that assessed students in each area was conducted. Task items contained in all the relevant studies were recorded in an item bank for possible inclusion in the assessment. This item bank together with a proposed experimental first draft was then forwarded to an expert panel for review. The revised draft was returned containing 21 task items assessing the pertinent content areas and utilised for piloting and further development of the screener. Two types of item format are utilised on the screener; multiple-choice known as selected-response (SR), and constructed-response, objective scoring (CROS) (Haladyna & Rodriguez, 2013). Of the SR items some used the Complex Multiple-Choice format where these items allow for answers that are incorrect, part correct, or fully correct (polytomous item). The remaining items used the Conventional Multiple-Choice format with four or five possible answers and only one of these is the absolute correct answer (dichotomous item). Part of the development of the screener was developing an SR format for existing constructed-response items identified in the literature. When creating an SR format, distractors are based on common errors to help inform teachers of the common errors and misconceptions made by their students. It is known that writing distractors is one of the most difficult aspects of item development and they often require revision from their first iteration (Haladyna & Rodriguez, 2013). The development of the initial distractors based on existing literature through to the final format based on the statistical analysis of the results is an important outcome of this study.

Finally, reporting of results to students must be an integrated part of the assessment design and development (Lane et al., 2016). An objective scoring system was established for the screener which then formed the basis for the statistical analysis conducted. Two forms of scores were developed for the items: first a cognitive score which awards a score when an item is correctly answered, and second, an error score which identifies a type of error associated with an item. A cognitive score (CS) is one which identifies a cognitive process, for example, knowledge, recall, interpretation, or synthesis (Anderson & Morgan, 2008). A CS was applied consistently to all items whereby a completely correct response was awarded 2, partly correct 1 and an incorrect response 0. Error scores have been developed for items to identify both potential procedural errors and misconceptions. An error score of '0' means that the student demonstrated evidence of understanding the concept and an error score of '1' reflects incomplete KSAs.

Methodology

Leedy and Ormrod (2010) succinctly define the validity of a measurement instrument as “the extent to which the instrument measures what it is intended to measure” (p. 31). The validity was established in terms of content, criterion, and construct validity, known as the trinitarian concept of validity (Foster, 2017). The focus in this paper is on the SR task items analyses which forms part of construct validity. According to Cohen et al., (2018, p. 257), there are two main stages in addressing construct validity; (i) ensuring the construct has been clearly and adequately defined and (ii) operationalising the constructs fairly. In defining the construct of initial algebra, the cognition vertex of the assessment triangle was used to establish the KSAs and a conceptual model as outlined above. Furthermore, the conceptual model was then aligned with the KSAs, which allowed for relevant items to be mapped to Junior Cycle specification to ensure the construct of interest was established clearly (O’ Brien & Ní Ríordáin, 2017).

The aim of this study is to validate the items for use with Irish second-year students specifically, to ensure the construct has been operationalised fairly for the population of interest (Cohen et al., 2018). It is important to note that subject matter expertise outweighs statistical guidelines when deciding if items should be retained, if it is believed they are measuring something important (Haladyna & Rodriguez, 2013). The revised draft of the screener returned from the expert panel was administered using pen and paper in a pilot school (n = 67) with a short survey. Task items were revised based on the results of this administration and feedback from teachers and students in the pilot school. Subsequently, the revised screener consisted of seventeen SR items and four CROS items. It was administered using pen and paper to 576 second-year students in 19 post-primary schools (29 classes) across Ireland in October 2016 and again in April 2017. There were two reasons for administering the screener twice to the same group of students; first was to enable the test-retest reliability measure of stability for the screener results (Cohen et al., 2018), and second was to measure the change in the students’ performance over the academic year.

Comprehensive item analyses utilising Classical Test Theory (CTT) were undertaken for the responses in the main study once each student had been assigned a complete set of CSs. First the facility index (FI) was calculated for each item to assess item difficulty. The FI equates to the proportion of correct responses for dichotomous items and ranges between 0 and 1, with an acceptable range from 0.3 up to 0.8 (Haladyna & Rodriguez, 2013). For polytomous items (a CS of 0, 1 or 2 in this study) the FI is calculated as the arithmetic mean for all respondents and accordingly ranges from 0 to 2 with an acceptable range of 0.6 up to 1.6 for this study (Finch, 2016). Subsequent analysis focused on item discrimination which is the relationship between the item response and performance on the screener overall (Haladyna & Rodriguez, 2013). In addition, multiple choice items were assessed for non-functioning distractors, that is a less than a 5% response rate, which should be removed (Ibid).

Findings

The discussion here focuses on the item analysis of SR items. Each item that had an FI outside the acceptable guidelines was identified, followed by the identification of items that did not discriminate well. Table 1 below details the results for the SR items. Each SR item and the content it assesses is listed with the associated FI and whether it discriminates well at each administration. Ten SR items were identified as requiring revision and/or further analysis. The analysis of distractors showed that six items had non-functioning distractors at both administrations. A final measure for item analysis is non-response and any item having greater than 15% of students not answering requires review (Anderson & Morgan, 2008). The items with non-functioning distractors are given together with the percentage of students who did not respond to the item on the screener at each administration. The cells highlighted in grey in Table 1 highlight the issues with the items. It is important to note at this point that evidence of students struggling with the subject of initial algebra had emerged from government reports and state examination results (O’ Brien & Ní Ríordáin, 2017). Therefore, these results and the FI for each item should be viewed in light of this information.

Table 1

Results of Item analyses for SR Items

Item number and content (CS; polytomous 0, 1,2; dichotomous 0,2)	Facility Index (FI)		Does the Item discriminate?		Non-functioning distractor		% Non-response		Revised Layout
	Oct	Apr	Oct	Apr	Oct	Apr	Oct	Apr	
2. Procedural Fraction Knowledge (0, 1, 2)	0.72	0.92	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	12.1	7.1	Yes ¹
3. Procedural Fraction Knowledge (0, 2)	0.38	0.46	Yes	Yes	No	No	12.3	10.5	Yes ²

4. Equivalent Fractions (0, 2)	0.42	0.49	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	8.3	5.7	Yes ²
5. Relational Fraction Knowledge (0, 2)	0.20	0.30	No	Yes	No	No	13.1	8.0	No
6. Proportional Reasoning (0, 2)	0.72	0.72	No	No	No	No	2.7	0.8	No
7. Exponents (0, 2)	0.36	0.33	No	No	No	No	16.4	9.2	Yes ²
8. Exponents and the Distributive Property (0, 2)	0.09	0.12	No	No	Yes	Yes	17.8	10.5	Yes ²
9. Order of Operations (0, 2)	0.30	0.36	Yes	Yes	No	No	9.7	6.1	Yes ²
10. Distributive Property (0, 1, 2)	0.71	0.79	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	12.6	8.0	Yes ¹
11. Comparing and Ordering Numbers (0, 2)	0.65	0.67	No	Yes	Yes	Yes	9.9	6.5	No
14. Variables (0, 2)	0.23	0.25	No	No	No	No	8.6	5.7	No
17. Expressions (0, 2)	0.47	0.56	Yes	Yes	No	Yes	18.9	12.4	Yes ²
18. Equation solving (0, 1, 2)	0.43	0.54	No	No	No	No	18.9	10.5	Yes ²
19. Equation solving (0, 1, 2)	0.88	1.10	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	17.3	8.2	Yes ³
20. Equation forming (0, 2)	0.22	0.25	No	No	No	No	15.3	7.1	No
21. Patterns – situation (0, 1, 2)	0.59	0.80	Yes	Yes	No	No	16.6	7.5	Yes ³
21. Patterns – form the equation (0, 1, 2)	0.34	0.51	Yes	Yes	No	No	18.9	9.2	Yes ³

Note. ¹ Items are polytomous, and their revised layout is discussed in the subsequent paragraph. ² Items are dichotomous, and their revised layout is discussed in the subsequent paragraph. ³ Items require further revision discussed below.

As evidenced in Table 1 many items need revision for a final version of the screener based on the item analyses. The use of Complex Multiple-Choice format for the pen and paper administration of the screener in the main study was not ideal however necessary for data inputting and analysis together with ease of scoring and identification of student errors. Most items on the screener are selected response and the most appropriate format for these items is to present three options in a vertical list (one correct and two distractors). However,

where there are more functioning distractors a four or five option vertical list is also appropriate (Haladyna & Rodriguez, 2013). All dichotomous SR items will be presented in this format with any non-functioning distractors removed². Polytomous items (more than one correct response) will have answers offered vertically with a YES/NO option printed beside each answer, where students are asked to circle a response to each answer¹. Based on the evidence from item analysis it is recommended that items should have their format and layout revised to ensure the construct of initial algebra is operationalised fairly.

Two items required more revision than others given non-functioning distractors, the layout of the answers, item difficulty and non-response particularly in the October administration³. The first of these items assessing equation solving was developed specifically for this study based on a study by Chung and Delacruz (2014). The item asks the student to identify the next correct step when solving the following equation; $7h - (3h - 2) = 38$. It is recommended this item is presented with only one correct answer $7h - 3h + 2 = 38$ as opposed to the two possible correct answers offered in the main study, $7h - 3h + 2 = 38$ and $7h + (-1)(3h - 2) = 38$. The first distractor, $7h - 3h - 2 = 38$, was the most chosen answer by students so this will remain as it identifies an important error in the application of the distributive property. A new distractor has been developed $-21h^2 - 14h = 38$ from observing the student workings which showed the attempt to multiply '7h' into the brackets.

The second item assessing patterns was a constructed response item from a study by Ayalon et al. (2015). The item was adapted for this study with the development of selected response answers. The issue of having more than one correct answer arises for this item, together with the amount of reading required. The student is asked how they would describe the process for finding the perimeter of one hundred hexagons, without knowing the perimeter of ninety-nine hexagons. Originally, responses were developed by the first author based on various student strategies identified by Ayalon et al. (2015). However, on consultation with the expert panel an additional correct option was added as it was in line with the methods of teaching patterns in Ireland. The item requires a lot of reading and therefore it cannot be said that knowledge of patterns alone is being assessed. It would be favourable to reduce the number of options to reduce word count as well as having the unfavourable two correct answers. The distractor analysis shows that the original correct answer as identified by Ayalon et al. (2015) in their study is preferable. Therefore, it is advisable to retain the item in its original format with 4 possible options. However, it is important to note that this item may need to be adjusted again after further administrations.

Discussion & Conclusion

This paper outlined the assessment triangle framework used to guide the development of a screener for initial algebra. The focus of this paper was on the validation of the SR items for use in the final version of the screener. The use of item analyses identified issues with several task items, and these have been amended accordingly. The distractors which are the incorrect answers to SR items are often the most challenging aspect of item development (Haladyna & Rodriguez, 2013). The development and testing of the distractors as part of this

research has been an important contribution to international research in addition to the development and validation of the task items for use in the Irish classroom.

This research has produced insights into students' issues with learning initial algebra, many of which were identified in the literature and are common to students worldwide. It confirms what Irish post-primary teachers have highlighted, that knowledge of fractions, decimal number magnitude, exponents, integers, order of operations and variables are key content areas where there is a lack of understanding (Shiel & Kelleher, 2017). The overall aim of developing the screener for use in the Irish classroom is to assist teachers identify student errors and possible root causes of these errors. The careful development of distractors for the SR task items on this screener enables this in an efficient manner. Therefore, the use of this screener as a formative assessment to create a profile of students' knowledge in the Irish classroom will be efficient and useful for teachers. It will allow for timely instructional decisions to help prevent and rectify skill gaps for students and is therefore an important contribution of this research (Ketterlin-Geller et al., 2019).

References

- Anderson, P., & Morgan, G. (2008). *Developing Tests and Questionnaires for a National Assessment of Educational Achievement*. The World Bank.
- Ayalon, M., Watson, A., & Lerman, S. (2015). Functions represented as linear sequential data: relationships between presentation and student responses. *Educational Studies in Mathematics*, 90(3), 321-339.
- Blanton, M., Brizuela, B. M., Stephens, A., Knuth, E., Isler, I., Gardiner, A. M., Stroud, R., Fonger, N., & Stylianou, D. (2018). Implementing a framework for early algebra. In Kieran C. (eds) *Teaching and learning algebraic thinking with 5-to 12-year-olds* (pp. 27-49). ICME-13 Monographs. Springer, Cham.
- Bloom, B. S. (1971). *Handbook on formative and summative evaluation of student learning*. McGraw-Hill.
- Bush, S. B., & Karp, K. S. (2013). Prerequisite algebra skills and associated misconceptions of middle grade students: A review. *The Journal of Mathematical Behavior*, 32(3), 613-632.
- Chung, G. K., & Delacruz, G. C. (2014). Cognitive readiness for solving equations. In O'Neil, H., Perez, R., Baker, E. (eds.), *Teaching and Measuring Cognitive Readiness* (pp. 135-148). Springer.
- Cohen, L., Mannion, L., & Morrison, K. (2018). *Research Methods in Education* (8th ed.). Routledge.
- Cronbach, L. J., & Meehl, P. E. (1955). Construct validity in psychological tests. *Psychological Bulletin*, 52(4), 281-302.
- Finch, W. H. (2016). *Applied psychometrics using SPSS and AMOS*. Information Age Publishing.

- Foster, C. (2017). Validity in educational and psychological assessment. *Research in Mathematics Education*, 19(2) 108-111.
- Haladyna, T. M., & Rodriguez, M. C. (2013). *Developing and validating test items*. Routledge.
- Kaput, J. J., Carraher, D. W., & Blanton, M. (2008). *Algebra in the early grades*. Routledge.
- Ketterlin-Geller, L. R., Shivraj, P., Basaraba, D., & Schielack, J. (2019). Universal screening for algebra readiness in middle school: Why, what, and does it work? *Investigations in Mathematics Learning*, 11(2), 120-133.
- Kieran, C. (2007). Learning and teaching algebra at the middle school through college levels. In F. K. Lester (Ed.), *Second handbook of research on mathematics Teaching and learning* (pp. 707-762). Information Age.
- Kieran, C., Pang, J., Schifter, D., & Fong Ng, S. (2016). *Early algebra: Research into its nature, its learning, its teaching*. Springer International Publishing.
- Lane, S., Raymond, M. R., & Haladyna, T. M. (2016). *Handbook of test development* (2nd ed.). Routledge.
- Leedy, P. D., & Ormrod, J. E. (2010). *Practical research planning and design* (9th ed.). Merrill Prentice Hall.
- NCCA. (2020). *Junior cycle mathematics guidelines for the classroom-based assessment and assessment task*. Retrieved from https://curriculumonline.ie/getmedia/f5af815d-5916-4dc9-bfda-4f3d73bc4787/Assessment_Guidelines_Mathematics.pdf
- Nichols, P. D., Kobrin, J. L., Lai, E., & Koepfler, J. (2017). The role of theories of learning and cognition in assessment design and development. In A. Rupp & J. Leighton (Eds.), *The handbook of cognition and assessment: Frameworks, methodologies, and applications* (pp. 13-40). John Wiley & Sons, Inc.
- O' Brien, A., & Ní Ríordáin, M. (2017). Examining difficulties in initial algebra: Pre-requisite and algebra content areas for Irish post-primary students.. In Dooley, T., & Gueudet, G. (Eds.). *Proceedings of the Tenth Congress of the European Society for Research in Mathematics Education* (pp. 1-8) (CERME10, February 1-5, 2017). DCU Institute of Education and ERME.
- Pellegrino, J. W., Chudowsky, N., & Glaser, R. (2001). *Knowing what students know: The science and design of educational assessment*. National Academy Press.
- Shiel, G., & Kelleher, C. (2017). *An evaluation of the impact of project maths on the performance of students in Junior Cycle mathematics*. Retrieved from https://www.erc.ie/wp-content/uploads/2018/07/PM_EvaluationStrand1.pdf